

OPTIMUM PROCESSING CONDITIONS FOR ULTRASONIC WELDING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

I. Fernandez Villegas^{1*}

¹Structural Integrity and Composites, Delft University of Technology

* Corresponding author (I.FernandezVillegas@tudelft.nl)

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Abstract

Ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites is a very interesting joining technique as a result of good quality joints, very short welding times and the fact that no foreign material (e.g. a metal mesh) is required at the welding interface in any case. This paper shows how on top of these advantages there is a consistent relationship between the feedback provided by modern ultrasonic welders and the weld strength. This relationship provides a tool for the fast and reliable definition of the optimum welding parameters for a certain material and welding configuration, which is usually a lengthy and costly process for other welding techniques.

1 Introduction

Ultrasonic welding is a very attractive assembling technique for thermoplastic composites since it is very fast, it does not require the use of foreign materials (e.g. a metal mesh) at the welding interface regardless the nature of the material being welded and it provides excellent quality joints. It is very well suited for welding of small areas and it can, in principle, be applied in a sequential manner for the welding of larger areas [1]. Consequently, ultrasonic welding is regarded as a very promising candidate for cost-effective assembly of mass-produced parts, such as clips and brackets in composite aircraft structures or composite automotive parts.

Mechanical pressure and a high-frequency low-amplitude vibration are applied to the parts to be ultrasonically welded. As a result, heat is generated at the welding interface via surface and viscoelastic friction. Energy directors are used to promote heat

generation in the interface between the parts to be joined. Energy directors are traditionally man-made resin protrusions on the welding surfaces. As a result of their smaller cross section, they undergo higher strains during the welding process and hence experience higher viscoelastic heating rates than the bulk material [2]. *Unreinforced thermoplastic* parts intended to be assembled through ultrasonic welding, a process widely used in various industries [3], are directly moulded with energy directors on the joining surfaces. In the case of the research on ultrasonic welding of *thermoplastic composite* parts, energy directors made out of the matrix resin have been traditionally moulded on the already consolidated adherends in a secondary production step [4]-[7]. Based on the procedures of the plastics industry, these energy directors are usually linear ridges with triangular, rectangular or semi-circular cross sections. The shape, size, number and orientation of the energy directors have been shown to have a major effect in the welding process and its results, since they influence heat generation and resin flow at the welding interface [6][7]. Quite recently Fernandez Villegas has presented in [8] successful results obtained with flat energy directors consisting of a loose matrix resin film placed at the welding interface. Preferential heating of the flat energy director occurs as a result of the lower compressive stiffness of the neat resin film as compared to the stiffness of the composite adherends. The use of flat energy directors greatly simplifies ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites and provides 100% welded areas without the need for extensive optimisation of the interfaces.

A significant advantage of ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites as compared to other

welding techniques is that it allows for in situ monitoring through process data. This possibility was first introduced by Benatar and Gutowski in [4], who analysed changes in the dissipated power and the acceleration of the base caused by the flow of the energy directors. More recently, Fernandez Villegas built on this idea and showed in [8] a clear correlation between the feedback of a microprocessor-controlled welder and the physical changes at the welding interface for flat-energy-director ultrasonic welding. In that study the dissipated power and the displacement of the sonotrode were found to define five distinct stages within the vibration phase of the welding process as shown in Figure 1 and described in what follows.

Figure 1. Five stages in the vibration phase of ultrasonic welding as defined by the dissipated power (black) and displacement of the sonotrode (grey) curves (CF/PEI, 300 N, 82.6 μ m).

- Stage 1: the energy director starts to heat up but no physical changes are observed at the welding interface yet. This stage features a continuous increase of the dissipated power until a maximum is reached.
- Stage 2: the flat energy director starts to locally melt as a hot-spot nucleation and growth process. Nucleation is mostly controlled by surface friction heating whereas viscoelastic heating has a predominant influence in the growth process. Stage 2 is characterised by a power decrease while the displacement of the sonotrode stays constant.
- Stage 3: the whole energy director is molten and starts to flow. This stage is characterised by a simultaneous increase of the power and of the displacement of the sonotrode.

- Stage 4: along with the flow of the energy director, the matrix in the uppermost layers of the composite adherends starts to (locally) melt. This stage features a plateau in the dissipated power.
- Stage 5: melting of the matrix in the adherends is predominant in this stage, which is characterised by a drop in the power.

The present paper is a step forward in the investigation of ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites in which the mechanical properties of the ultrasonically welded joints are correlated with the dissipated power and the displacement of the sonotrode as provided by the ultrasonic welder. Such a correlation is a very important tool for fast definition of the optimum processing parameters for a certain material and welding configuration, which is usually a lengthy and costly process for other welding techniques.

2 Experimental procedures

In the present research work, single-lap thermoplastic composite samples were individually welded within different stages of the ultrasonic welding process. Relations between the strength of the welds, the physical transformations at the interface and the feedback from the welder were sought. Different combinations of welding force and vibration amplitude were used to further investigate these relations. The materials and procedures followed in this experimental research are described in detail in what follows.

2.1 Adherends

The material used in this study was Cetex CF/PEI (carbon-fibre reinforced polyetherimide) with 5 harness satin fabric reinforcement. $[0/90]_{3S}$ laminates (1.92 mm nominal final thickness) were consolidated in a hot-platen press at 320°C and 20 bar for 30 min. 100 mm x 25.4 mm samples were cut from the laminates with an abrasive saw to produce single-lap welded specimens. The main apparent orientation of the fibres on the outer surfaces of the samples was parallel to their longitudinal direction. After cutting, the samples were dried in an oven at 135°C for 6 hours following the recommendations of the manufacturer.

2.2 Welding

A 20 kHz Rinco Dynamic micro-processor controlled ultrasonic welder was used to weld individual samples in a single-lap configuration with $12.7 \times 25.4 \text{ mm}^2$ overlap area. This ultrasonic welder, with a maximum power output of 3000 W, automatically adjusts the power delivered during the welding process in order to keep the vibration amplitude constant. It also allows for a certain range of amplitude values for a fixed sonotrode/booster configuration. For the 1:1 booster and 1:2 sonotrode used in this study, nine peak-to-peak amplitude levels ranging from 51.8 to 86.2 μm were available. The titanium sonotrode was cylindrical with 40 mm-diameter at the edge in contact with the samples to be welded.

Shifting of the adherends during the welding process was prevented through a custom-made welding jig (Figure 2). This welding jig also prevented bending of the upper adherend during the melting and flow of the energy director by allowing the adherend to slide vertically throughout the welding process.

Figure 2. Ultrasonic welder and welding jig used in this study. 1: sonotrode, 2: platform that is allowed to slide vertically, 3: clamp for the upper adherend (attached to 2), and 4: clamp for the lower adherend.

As described in the 'Introduction', flat energy directors, i.e. flat matrix resin layers, were used to concentrate heat generation at the welding interface instead of the traditional triangular energy directors described in literature. As shown later in this paper, these flat resin layers proved to successfully concentrate heating at the welding interface and to provide 100% welded areas. The flat energy directors were manufactured in a hot platen press at

260°C out of five 50 μm -thick neat PEI layers. The final thickness of the flat energy directors was 0.25 mm. After being cut to size (slightly bigger than the overlap area), they were oven-dried at 135 min for 1 h.

The minimum and maximum vibration amplitudes for the booster/sonotrode configuration used in this study, i.e. 51.8 μm and 86.2 μm were evaluated. The welding force, which was kept constant throughout the vibration phase of the process, was either 300 N or 1500 N. These values almost covered the whole range of welding forces available in the ultrasonic welder. The duration of the vibration time was indirectly controlled through the differential displacement of the sonotrode, which, as shown later in this paper, was found to provide highly consistent results. This controlling parameter is called travel hereafter. The solidification force and time were respectively 1000 N and 4 s for every set of welding parameters.

2.3 Testing and evaluation

The welded samples were mechanically tested following the ASTM D 1002 standard (five samples per set of welding conditions) with a cross-head speed of 0.13 mm/min. The apparent single-lap shear strength (LSS) of the welds was calculated as the maximum load divided by the total overlap area.

Micrographic cross-sections along the length of overlap at the middle of the welding area were analysed to assess the changes in the welding interface and in the composite adherends in different stages of the welding process. Fractography was used to evaluate the main failure modes in the different welding conditions.

Finally, the dissipated power and the displacement of the sonotrode during the vibration phase of the welding process were obtained as feedback from the ultrasonic welder. The vibration time was also provided by the welder.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Power/displacement curves and weld strength

Figure 3 displays representative power curves for travel values ranging from 12% to 100% of the thickness of the flat energy director at 300 N

welding force and $86.2\ \mu\text{m}$ vibration amplitude. The corresponding displacement curves are not shown in order to improve clarity. However the beginning of stage 3 (characterised by a simultaneous increment of the power and of the displacement) is depicted by vertical lines drawn onto the power curves.

Figure 3. Power curves for different travel values (from 12% to 100%) and corresponding lap shear strength values for 300 N welding force and $86.2\ \mu\text{m}$ vibration amplitude. In order to improve clarity, the power curves are shifted upwards and the displacement curves are not presented. Vertical lines are drawn instead on the power curves to indicate the beginning of stage 3.

As seen in this Figure, 12% travel leads to welding processes that end in stage 3, 20 and 40% travel result in stage-4 welding processes (very beginning of stage 4 for 20% travel) and 60, 80 and 100% lead to stage-5 welding. Only one power curve per travel value is depicted in Figure 3, however these results were consistently obtained for all the samples welded in this study. To illustrate this, Figure 4 shows the power curves for different samples welded under 20%-travel (stage-4 welding) and 80% travel (stage-5 welding).

Figure 4. Power curves for different samples welded at 20% travel (left) and 80% travel (right), 300 N welding force and $86.2\ \mu\text{m}$ vibration amplitude. The vertical lines indicate the beginning of stage 3 as defined by the simultaneous increase of power and displacement.

Figure 3 also displays the LSS for the different travel values investigated. The weld strength is seen to increase during stage 3 until it reaches a

maximum ($37.3 \pm 1.6\ \text{MPa}$) towards the end of stage 4 (40% travel). In stage 5 the weld strength features a decreasing trend. The scatter in the LSS values is below 8% (coefficient of variation) in every case.

Representative fracture surfaces are shown in Figures 5 to 10. At 12% and 20% travel (Figures 5 and 6) the remaining energy director, which still shows in cross sections as a quite thick and distinct weldline at the interface (see Figure 11), can be clearly identified in the fracture surfaces. It mainly remains on one of the fracture surfaces and it primarily shows fibre imprints on its surface, while the opposite fracture surface shows relatively bare fibres. The imprints on the surface of the energy director are, as shown in the SEM details of Figures 5 and 6, deeper for 20% than for 12% travel. For 12% travel patches of energy director without any fibre imprints as well as clear traces of neat resin at the fracture line of the energy director are also often found (Figure 5).

Figure 6. Fracture surface (left) and SEM detail (right) for 300 N, $86.2\ \mu\text{m}$ and 20% travel. The circle indicates the approximate location of the detail.

Figure 5. Fracture surface (left) and SEM detail (right) for 300 N, $86.2\ \mu\text{m}$ and 20% travel. The circle indicates the approximate location of the detail.

At 40% travel fracture surfaces show torn fibre bundles sometimes being pulled out from the adherends (Figure 7). Traces of the energy director are not easily found on these fracture surfaces, which as shown in Figure 11 already has a thickness

similar to the resin-rich areas between the layers of the adherends.

Figure 7. Fracture surface (left) and SEM detail (right) for 300 N, 86.2 μm and 40% travel. The circle indicates the approximate location of the detail.

Figure 8. Fracture surface (left) and SEM detail (right) for 300 N, 86.2 μm and 60% travel. The circle indicates the approximate location of the detail.

Figure 9. Fracture surface at 80% travel (300 N welding force and 86.2 μm amplitude).

Figure 10. Fracture surface at 100% travel (300 N welding force and 86.2 μm amplitude).

At 60% travel, fracture surfaces feature deep laminate tearing and some deformation of the fibre bundles closer to the welding interface (Figure 8). As the travel increases, increasing deformation of the fibre bundles can be seen in the fracture surfaces, which tend to show planar failure as opposed to deep laminate tearing (see Figures 9 and 10 for 80 and 100% travel).

Looking back at the evolution of the weld strength in Figure 3, the gradual LSS increase in stages 3 and 4 can be attributed to several potential factors. Firstly, the enhanced molecular diffusion and therefore the creation of a stronger bond as the matrix in the

uppermost layers of the adherends starts to melt. On the other hand, the decrease in the thickness of the weldline could be expected to decrease to a certain extent the peak stresses at the edges of the overlap during single lap shear testing, as it is known for adhesive bonded joints [9]. The gradual decrease in LSS after the maximum reached within stage 4 is mainly attributed to the deformation of the unsupported fibre bundles under vibration when big areas of matrix melt. This effect mostly weakens the interface and its vicinity and tends to cause failure in that area leading to relatively planar fracture surfaces. The occurrence of deep laminate tearing, especially at 60% travel, is attributed to the kinking of the uppermost layers of the adherends at the edges of the overlap as a result of local matrix flow [8] as shown in Figure 12. This phenomenon brings along some porosity within the adherends most probably caused by the flow of resin and/or the decompaction of areas not subjected to the welding pressure. This porosity is believed to act as a starting point for the tearing of the adherends. The potential effect of the kinks on the stresses at the edges of the overlap during the single lap shear test is unknown.

Figure 11. Cross-section micrographs (centre of the overlap) for 20% travel (left) and 40% travel (right) at 300 N welding force and 86.2 μm . Arrows indicating the position of the weldline.

Figure 12. Cross-section micrographs (edge of the overlap) for 60% travel (left) and 80% travel (right) at 300 N welding force and 86.2 μm vibration amplitude showing kinking of the uppermost layers of the lower substrate and associated porosity.

3.2 Effect of the welding parameters

As discussed in [8], changes in the main welding parameters, i.e. the welding force and the vibration amplitude, do not have a significant effect in the overall shape of the power/displacement curves and in the stages they define. Moreover Figures 13 and 14 show that when the amplitude is decreased to 51.8 μm or the force is increased to 1500 N, the relationship between power curves and weld strength remains as explained previously. Consequently, the weld strength increases in stages 3 and 4 until it reaches a maximum towards the end of this last stage and it gradually decreases in stage 5. The average LSS values obtained in these two cases are very similar to the ones presented in the previous section. As for the dispersion in the weld strength, for 300 N-56.2 μm the scatter is below 4.5% and for 1500 N -86.2 μm it is below 7.5%.

Figure 13. Power curves for different travel values (from 20% to 100%) and corresponding lap shear strength values for 300 N welding force and 51.8 μm vibration amplitude.

Figure 14. Power curves for different travel values (from 20% to 100%) and corresponding lap shear strength values for 1500 N welding force and 86.2 μm vibration amplitude.

Changing the force or the amplitude has however a significant impact in the duration of the vibration phase and in the dissipated power levels [8]. Figure 15 presents typical 100%-travel power curves for the three sets of parameters in this study as well as LSS versus average vibration time for all the travel values in this research. The time shift in the power

curves as well as in the development of the weld strength is clearly visible in this Figure.

Figure 15. Representative 100%-travel curves (left) and LSS versus vibration time curves (right) for the three combinations of welding parameters in this study: (a) 300 N-86.2 μm , (b) 300 N-51.8 μm , and (c) 1500 N-86.2 μm . Error bars in the LSS graph are not presented for improved clarity.

Apart from this obvious time-shift in weld strength development, a closer inspection of Figures 3, 13 and 14 reveals that the travel value for maximum weld strength is not the same for every set of welding parameters. As shown in Figure 16, increasing of the welding force from 300 N to 1500 N (86.2 μm amplitude) has the effect of pushing the initial increase of LSS, and thus the maximum LSS value, to higher travel values. Likewise, decreasing of the amplitude of vibration from 86.2 μm to 51.8 μm (300 N welding force) also has the effect of slightly delaying the occurrence of the maximum LSS. Its main effect though is providing better strength retention at high travel values.

Figure 16. Average LSS versus travel for the three sets of welding conditions studied in this paper (A9=86.2 μm amplitude and A1=51.8 μm).

The evolution of the fracture surfaces with increasing travel for 300 N welding force and 51.8 μm amplitude is very similar to what explained in the previous section for 300 N and 86.2 μm . The main difference is lower deformation of the fibre bundles at the highest travel values. Figure 17 illustrates this through a 100%-travel fracture surface. In the case of 1500 N welding force and 86.2 μm amplitude fibre tearing is overall less pronounced and no deep laminate tearing can be observed at any travel value. Figure 18 shows considerably less fibre tearing on a 100%-travel surface as compared to the other sets of welding conditions under study.

Based on these results, the fact that a higher travel is necessary to reach maximum weld strength for high force-high amplitude conditions is believed to be caused by the very short vibration time. When the welding force is high there is a much more effective triggering of viscoelastic heating all over the interface through improved surface friction [8][10]. As a result, the time required for the energy director to fully melt and to start flowing is significantly diminished. When the vibration time is short, there is less time available for heat to be transferred to the adherends. Figure 19 shows an indication of the through-the-thickness extent of the heat affected zone (HAZ) at 100%-travel for 1500 N-86.2 μm and 100% travel for 300 N-86.2 μm based on the cross section of welds non-solidified after vibration. Even though viscoelastic heat generation is expected to be the same in both cases as a result of the same vibration amplitude [8], the HAZ is not as deep for the high welding force. Therefore melting of the matrix in the uppermost layers of the adherends, and hence achieving improved molecular diffusion along with the creation of strong bonds, will require longer vibration times and thus higher travel values in that case. The fact that fibre tearing occurs to a much lesser extent during failure of the high force-high amplitude welds indicates that the bonds formed in this case are nevertheless not as strong as the ones formed in lower welding force or lower amplitude conditions.

The more effective weld-strength retention at high travel values for low force-low amplitude welding is attributed to a lower deformation of the fibre

bundles at the welding interface once the matrix is molten. This directly results from the lower welding amplitude. The lower welding amplitude also decreases the viscoelastic heating rate, which could be the reason why strength development is slightly shifted towards higher travel values as compared to 300 N-86.2 μm .

Figure 17. Fracture surface at 100% travel for 300 N and 51.8 μm showing less fibre-bundle deformation than the one in Figure 10 (300 N and 86.2 μm)

Figure 18. Fracture surface at 100% travel for 1500 N and 86.2 μm showing less fibre tearing than the ones in Figures 10 (300 N and 86.2 μm) and 19 (300 N and 51.8 μm)

Figure 19. Cross-section micrographs of samples welded at 100% travel, 1500 N and 86.2 μm (left) and 100% travel, 300 N and 86.2 μm (right) that did not undergo solidification after vibration. De-consolidation voids can be observed in the areas that reached temperatures above T_g during the vibration. For 1500 N-86.2 μm voids are observed in the first (uppermost) composite ply, whereas for 300 N-86.2 μm they can as well be found in the second composite ply. Note that just one adherend is presented since the weld opened up after pressure release.

4 Conclusions

The main conclusions drawn from this study on the optimum processing conditions for ultrasonic welding of CF/PEI thermoplastic composites are the following.

- There is a direct relationship between the power/displacement curves generated during each welding cycle and the strength developed by the welded joints. The weld strength increases during stage 3 of the process (characterised by flow of the

energy director) until a maximum is reached towards the end of stage 4 (simultaneous occurrence of flow of the energy director and melting of the matrix in the uppermost layers of the adherends). Melting of the matrix positively contributes to molecular diffusion across the weldline and hence to the creation of strong welds. After this maximum, the strength gradually decreases during stage 5 (where mostly melting of the matrix occurs) primarily as a result of the deformation of the fibre bundles under the vibration.

- The relationship between the strength and the power/displacement curves is independent of the welding conditions, i.e. welding force and amplitude. However, there are differences in how the strength is developed as a function of the travel. Some of these differences result from the fact that when the welding force is high there is very little time available for the heat generated at the interface to be transferred to the adherends. Consequently, melting of the matrix along with higher strength welds only occur at higher travel values. Likewise, decreasing of the amplitude of vibration has a direct influence in the deformation of the fibre bundles and hence in strength retention at high travel values.

- The travel or displacement of the sonotrode can be effectively used to control the duration of the vibration phase of the flat-energy-director ultrasonic welding process. For a given set of welding conditions a fixed travel leads to welding cycles that consistently end at the same power stage. As a result, similar fracture features and little dispersion in strength values are observed in such welds.

- Apart from in situ monitoring of the welding process, the power/displacement curves can be effectively used to indirectly define an optimum range for the travel of the sonotrode given a certain set of welding force and vibration amplitude. As a result, the definition of processing windows for the ultrasonic welding process is greatly simplified.

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6 References

- [1] H.M. Lu and A. Benatar "Sequential ultrasonic welding of PEEK/Graphite composite parts". *Proceedings of the Annual Technical Conference ANTEC*, Montreal, Canada, 1991.
- [2] H. Potente "Ultrasonic Welding – Principles and Theory". *Materials and Design*. 5 (5), pp 228-234, 1984.
- [3] D. Grewel, A. Benatar and J. Park *Plastics and Composites Welding Handbook. Hansen Gardner Publications*, Munich, Germany, 2003.
- [4] A. Benatar and T.G. Gutowski "Ultrasonic welding of PEEK graphite APC-2 composites" *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 29, No. 23. pp 1705-1721, 1989.
- [5] E.C. Eveno, J.W. Gillespie Jr. "Experimental investigation of ultrasonic welding of graphite reinforced polyetheretherketone composites". In: *Proceedings of National SAMPE Technical Conference*, Atlantic City, NJ, USA, 1989.
- [6] B.K. Harras, C. Cole et al. "Optimization of the ultrasonic welding of PEEK-carbon composites". *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp 174-182, 1996.
- [7] S.J. Liu and I.T. Chang "Factors affecting the joint strength of ultrasonically welded polypropylene composites". *Polymer Composites*, Vol 22, No. 1, pp 132-141, 2001.
- [8] I. Fernandez Villegas "In situ monitoring of ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites through power and displacement data" *Journal of Thermoplastic Composites* (in press), 2013.
- [9] Gleich D.M., van Tooren M.J.L., Beukers A. "Analysis and evaluation of bondline thickness effects on failure load in adhesively bonded structures" *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, Vol. 15, No. 9, pp 1901-1101, 2001.
- [10] Z. Zhang, X. Wang et al. "Study on heating process of ultrasonic welding for thermoplastics". *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, Vol. 23, No. 5, pp 647-664, 2010.